

Work Package 1 – Shared modelling framework and learnings

D1.2 – Description of scientific methods

Task 1.3 – Methods for Life Cycle Impact Assessment

Guide on the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) for bio-based products – Biodiversity

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This document is a part of the ALIGNED project (grant no. 101059430) deliverable D1.2. It contains the practical approaches to harmonize and apply the latest recommendations on the climate change impacts’ assessment phase of LCAs within the ALIGNED project.

PROJECTS DETAILS			
Project title	Aligning Life Cycle Assessment methods and bio-based sectors for improved environmental performance.		
Project acronym	ALIGNED	Start / Duration	01/10/2022 – 36 months
Type of Action	RIA	Website	www.alignedproject.eu

DELIVERABLE DETAILS			
Dissemination level	Public	Nature	Report
Due date (M)	M18 (March/2024)	Submission date	31/03/2024

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DOCUMENT HISTORY			
Date	Version	Name	Changes
02/02/2024	v0.1	Draft for internal review	First draft
18/02/2024	v0.2	Guide Task 1.3 - Biodiversity	Extended review
19/03/2024	v1.0	Final version	
07/05/2024	v1.1	Final version	Minor corrections (typos & reference style)

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Executive summary

This document presents practical approaches to harmonize and apply the latest recommendations on the impact assessment phase of LCAs within the ALIGNED project. It specifically addresses **impacts on biodiversity**, of foremost importance for bio-based production. The document proposes a synthesis of the latest research and existing frameworks, and elaborates a guidance formulated as a tiered approach, as for all the components of the methodological framework of ALIGNED WP1. It describes the strategies for the construction of impact pathways from environmental intervention to damages on biodiversity leading to spatially explicit characterization Factors. Two driving forces on biodiversity loss, namely Climate Change and Land Use / Land Use Change (LULUC), are further investigated in operational LCIA methods and additional recent studies. Recommendations for users, following a 3-tier approach, are provided at the end of the document.

Acronyms and abbreviations

ABBREVIATIONS	Description
CF	Characterization Factor
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GTP	Global Temperature Potential
GWP	Global Warming Potential
IAM	Integrated Assessment Model
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LULUC	Land Use and Land Use Change
MSA	Mean Species Abundance
PAF	Potentially Affected Fraction
PDF	Potentially Disappeared Fraction
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway
SAR	Species-Area Relationship
SSP	Shared Socio-economic Pathways

1. Assessing damages on biodiversity

Biodiversity is the diversity of living organisms. It is assessed by considering the diversity of species, the diversity of genes within each species, and the organization and distribution of ecosystems. In LCA, biodiversity can be considered as a synonym of ‘Ecosystem Quality’, which is one of the three currently assessed Areas of Protection (along with Human Health and Natural Resources). Hence in the LCIA’s conceptual framework, impacts (or damages) to biodiversity are computed through endpoint characterization factors (CF), positioning at the end of the pathway linking an environmental intervention¹ to impacts to damages on areas of protections pathways (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Substance to damage modelling in LCIA frameworks

1.1. Metrics for biodiversity loss

The concept of biodiversity is multi-dimensional: ‘global’ biodiversity is more likely to refer to species extinction, while ‘local’ or ‘regional’ biodiversity is rather a proxy for ecosystem functioning (Verones et al., 2020). The classification / grouping of species is also highly variable: it can be processed e.g. throughout taxonomic groups at various taxonomic ranks, or throughout habitats at different scales (global habitat types such as terrestrial, freshwater or marine; regional biomes; local ecoregion (Olson et al., 2001); etc.). Another dimension of biodiversity is related to the functioning aspects of living organisms (complexity of a given ecosystem’s structure; diversity of species playing a given role within a given ecosystem; genetic diversity

¹ The term ‘environmental intervention’ refers to either a substance emission to the natural environment, a resource extraction from the natural environment, or land occupation or transformation.

within a given species (Pereira et al., 2013). Therefore, integrating all kind of man-made induced damages (and benefits) to biodiversity into a single indicator remains challenging.

The LCIA community is nonetheless converging towards an endpoint unit that reflects an 'increase in global extinction risk over a certain exposure of time' (Verones et al., 2020). Typical endpoint units for damage assessment on ecosystem quality are Potentially Disappeared Fraction of species over time (PDF.yr), Potentially Affected Fraction of species over time (PAF.yr) or absolute number of species lost over time (species.yr). It is worth noticing that outside of the LCA framework, other approaches seem to prefer the MSA indicators (Mean Species Abundance), a relative metric quantifying the average remaining abundance of all species in each area in comparison to an undisturbed situation (see e.g. Schipper et al., 2016).

1.2. Building characterization factors

The role of biodiversity characterization factors (CF) is to provide LCIA methods with easy-to-use proxies suitable to compute in LCA software to translate a pulse environmental intervention (or a distribution of) into a damage on ecosystem quality (see Figure 1). For example, SO₂ emissions potentially generate acid rains, leading to the acidification of lakes and further increase in mortality of fishes, potentially affecting freshwater biodiversity. Endpoint-related CFs directly translate the environmental intervention into its potential damage through a single CF (e.g. a given GHG emission, in specific conditions, leads to a given increase of PDF; Iordan et al., 2023). Midpoint-to-endpoint CFs translate impact categories provided in the LCIA methods into damages to the Area of Protection 'ecosystem quality', e.g. traducing a change in temperature as characterized at the midpoint level for climate change, into PDF.yr.

There are five acknowledged drivers of biodiversity losses: climate change, pollutions (which can take the form of chemicals and active compounds release, nutrients deposition, plastics, etc.), land use changes (leading to habitat loss due to e.g. artificialization and fragmentation), overexploitation of biotic resources, introduction of invasive species (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). However, not all impact pathways damaging biodiversity are scientifically documented with sufficient degree of robustness nor evidence (Verones et al., 2020), hampering the comprehensive inclusion of biodiversity-related impacts in LCA studies. Furthermore, such damages depend on the spatial and temporal pattern of the various environmental interventions (Iordan et al., 2023), and often adopt a non-linear, time-distorted response curve. Therefore, despite continuous efforts and progress, accurately assessing damages of human activities on biodiversity goes much beyond the capabilities of available LCA software and databases (e.g. ecoinvent is available at the country level at most). Noticeably, the PEF framework (European Commission, 2021) requires assessing impacts to biodiversity as a qualitative complement to LCA-based reporting; this illustrates the fact that current initiatives to report and assess impacts of business activities to biodiversity do not rely solely on current LCA framework.

1.3. Current LCIA methods to assess biodiversity

Typically, CF are derived per driver at the endpoint indicator level (Figure 1), and not all are considered. Many methods have been proposed and reviewed recently, but so far there is no international consensus on which CF should be used in LCA studies. The review developed by

Damiani et al. (2023) classified 23 available LCIA methods depending on how these cover the impacts on biodiversity, across five criteria: drivers of biodiversity loss (i.e. 'pressures'); types of ecosystems considered; taxonomic groups, biodiversity variable classes; and fundamental biodiversity aspects.

They highlight that among the five biodiversity loss drivers, most assessment methods include Land Use, Climate Change and Pollution; this is the case of operational LCIA methods such as ReCiPe (Huijbregts et al., 2017), Impact World+ (Bulle et al., 2019) and LC-IMPACT (Verones et al., 2020). Yet, these are based on different considerations when it comes to temporal and spatial discretization, with a partial coverage of biodiversity among taxonomic groups. The other mentioned methods that assess these three drivers are directly derived from – or are 'plugs-in' for – these operational LCIA methods. This suggests that a lot of research effort is currently being operated within the LCIA community, and current versions of operational LCIA methods are likely to be superseded by newer, more comprehensive and accurate versions.

The two remaining biodiversity loss drivers, namely Overexploitation and Invasive Species are much less considered. In fact, only one method reviewed by Damiani et al. (2023) takes them into account (Asselin et al., 2020); but it remains a semi-quantitative approach that cannot be transposed into the LCA framework.

1.3.1. Characterization of land use impacts in LCIA methods

Land use is the most represented driver among available LCIA biodiversity methods. In total, eleven LCIA methods consider land use as the only biodiversity loss driver, with different levels of spatial resolution and temporal dynamics. Abundant, high resolution, satellite-based maps and data significantly triggered the enhancement of LCIA methods in the recent past. Interestingly, Damiani et al. (2023) notice that the two most common data sources in the reviewed methods are GLOBIO (Schipper et al., 2016) and IUCN (www.iucnredlist.org).

Most LCA-based methods developed Land Use and Land-Use Change (LULUC) characterization factors from the well-established Surface-to-Area Relationship (SAR). ReCiPe proposes a set of non-spatially explicit CFs, calculated by comparing average biodiversity in man-made occupied and transformed land, with an original, pristine natural environment. This approach has been consistently revised in the LC-Impact method (Chaudhary et al., 2015; Verones et al., 2020), where spatially explicit CFs were introduced by combining high-resolution Vulnerability Scores for 5 taxonomic groups provided by IUCN and Land Stress indicators per type of LULUC, for each of the 804 ecoregions depicted in Olson et al. (2001). This method was then recommended by the UNEP-SETAC to assess biodiversity loss in LCA (Frischknecht et al., 2016).

An updated version of these CFs increased again their spatial resolution (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2018), by using an updated version of SAR, namely Countryside SAR (Pereira & Daily, 2006), and by introducing three different levels of land use intensity by human activities. The resulting database, a comprehensive set of >60,000 CFs for Land Occupation (and the same amount for Land Transformation), shows that such greater accuracy leads to smaller uncertainty intervals. They are fully available as Supporting Information in (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2018).

Despite this considerable improvement in LCIA related to one of the main drivers of biodiversity loss, this dataset suffers from lack of field data on species monitoring, so it is likely

to be improved in the future. Another potential limit of the SAR approach to derive CFs for LULUC, is the difficulty to consistently include other significant man-made disturbance on local ecosystems such as encroachment and land fragmentation. Suggestions exist to overcome this issue. For example, a Forest Fragmentation Potential index has been calculated at various geographical scales. This index relies on the notion of metapopulation capacity (see e.g. CDC Biodiversité, 2020; Larrey-Lassalle et al., 2018). As mentioned by Frischknecht et al. (2016), accurately evaluating biodiversity loss from LULUC requires the highest level of resolution, and ‘farm-specific knowledge’. Although the latest developments in CFs for LULUC significantly improve background information for LCA practitioners, it remains recommended to use other tools to assess biodiversity loss at local scale.

In addition, it is well-known that responses of biodiversity to drivers are complex, with threshold effects, feedback loops and time-lag. Although dealing with temporal variation might be addressed in LCA by frequent updates of CFs – assuming frequent updates in biodiversity monitoring. But the consistent incorporation of dynamic aspects of LULUC impacts into the LCIA phase suffers from the same operational limitations as integrating the dynamic aspects of climate change (see guide_cc).

1.3.2. Using IAMs in the assessment of biodiversity impacts

One of the goals of Integrated Assessment Modelling (IAM) is to account for the dynamic interactions between human activities and the Biosphere. Various approaches have been recently proposed with a specific focus on LULUC. For example, Chen et al. (2020) rely on IPCC’s ‘Shared Socio-economic Pathways’ (SSP) and ‘Representative Concentration Pathways’ (RCP) to build projections on land cover changes across the globe with a very high spatial resolution. IAMs can be used for sector-specific projections. For example, potential indirect LULUC from development of silviculture for large-scale construction purposes were also investigated using MAgPIE model (Mishra et al., 2022). At the scale of the whole technosphere, the premise model (Sacchi et al., 2022) aims at delivering a ‘dynamic’ version ofecoinvent adaptable to various IAMs, enabling their users to enhance the description and evolution of global human activities and interactions with the natural environment in different prospective scenarios.

While these advances may trigger a new paradigm to build spatially explicit, scenario-dependent Life Cycle Inventories, they generally do not investigate the potential temporal variation of impact pathways, either delivering LCI results only, or relying on currently operational LCIA methods with ‘static’ CFs to assess damages on biodiversity. Thus, they generally fail in considering threshold effects and temporal inertia in the relationships between the biosphere and land occupation by human activities.

1.3.3. Evaluating biodiversity loss from Climate Change

Climate Change is another major driver for biodiversity loss, both on global and local scales. In current operational LCIA methods, impact pathways from GHG emissions and biodiversity loss are modelled as follows:

In ReCiPe 2016 and in LC-Impact, GHG emissions lead to midpoint impact CF of climate change, expressed in kgCO₂eq. Then, a midpoint-to-endpoint CF is calculated in several steps. First, marginal time-integrated temperature change from the emission of 1kg CO₂ is calculated for three time horizons (related to the cultural perspectives proposed by the method); then, this

factor is multiplied by an estimation of the total number of terrestrial species (obtained by combining total terrestrial land area and average species density) and by an effect factor denoting the marginal increase of PDF due to a marginal increase in temperature. The latter data is taken from (Urban, 2015). The same approach is used to develop CFs of freshwater biodiversity loss from climate change, using a model that includes change in water discharge due to climate change (Hanafiah et al., 2011). It is important here to notice that the original models and calculations provide more detailed, useful data such as river-basin specific and GHG specific CFs (Hanafiah et al., 2011) and terrestrial biodiversity loss per taxonomic group depending on RCP scenarios (Urban, 2015). However, supposedly for the sake of harmonization, only global averages were used to build ReCiPe / LC-Impact CFs.

In the Impact World + model (IW+, Bulle et al., 2019), the general framework enables to assess the temporal evolution of fate factors, exposure factors, exposure response factors and severity factors (the product of these 4 factors give the CFs) for most of environmental intervention leading to damages of ecosystem quality – expressed in PDF.m2.yr. Whenever possible, each of these factors are computed with the highest possible level of spatial resolution. Hence, this structure delivers damage score for accounted environmental intervention and flow-to-damage pathways at the local level, for each ecosystem type and taxonomic group considered. Damages are ultimately compiled at the global level, preventing the users from information loss by using global averages as CFs². Regarding damages on ecosystem quality from climate change, IW+ relies on time-integrated global temperature change potential (GTP) of GHGs (as opposed to ReCiPe and LC-Impact, which rely on GWP100 of GHGs); it is worth noticing that time-integrated GWP is also used, to calculate damages on ecosystem services (Area of Protection: Resources). IW+ also includes damage generated by ocean acidification due to climate change. However, although fate and exposure factors (i.e. changes in radiative forcing, surface temperature or ocean pH) are time-integrated, it remains unclear whether it is also the case for exposure response factors and severity factors or if the latter are ‘static’ parameters.

An example of state-of-the-art biodiversity CFs for climate change drivers can be found in Jordan et al., (2023). The authors calculated the fraction of marine & terrestrial (including freshwater) species affected, per taxonomic group and per geographical grid cell due to a change in temperature each year. They propose biodiversity CF for 20 GHGs, several species group, geographies and climate scenarios for 2050 and 2100 horizon. The novelty of this approach is that it considers the speed of temperature rise while computing the cumulative amount of affected species, thus getting around the limitations of indicators like GWP and GTP from which damage assessment highly depends on the Time Horizon considered (see ALIGNED T1.3 repository *LCIA-guide_CC* file). However, damages are expressed in terms of PAF – not in PDF as in LC-Impact.

² IW+ also provide regional and global averages, in order to include non-spatially explicit environmental interventions.

2. Recommendations – tiered approach

As explained in the previous section, a robust approach encompassing all drivers, ecosystems, species and biodiversity quality dimensions is far from being operationally available in LCA software.

LCIA methods are regularly updated to incorporate latest developments in that matter; their current general framework coupled with high-resolution satellite data leaves room for spatially explicit CFs for both foreground and background data, which might improve impact assessment of LULUC in future studies. However, routine use of spatial CFs also requires spatially explicit LCI background database, which in turn requires a significant update of existing datasets.

In contrast, climate change impacts do not depend on the place of emissions. Modelling damages on ecosystem quality can thus be done for any GHG emission profile without any spatial information. However, the severity of damages from GHG emissions also depend on future scenarios, which may bring additional complexity to results interpretation.

Depending on the level of practitioner's expertise and available time, three levels of methodological complexity can be proposed for application.

2.1. Tier 1 recommendations

For least experienced users, ALIGNED recommendations are to use current operational LCIA methods such as ReCiPe and IW+, already implemented in LCA software such as SimaPro and OpenLCA. LC-Impact method is currently being prepared for operational use in the two software.

The Tier 1 approach keeps the practitioner within a 'safe operability mode', since LCIA methods may easily lead to biased interpretation. The consistency of operational methods is a necessary safety belt that may disappear when mixing LCIA methods with each other or using novel CFs that are not fully integrated into a whole, homogeneous pack. This is especially the case for damages on biodiversity loss, for which impact pathways need more research efforts and documentation.

It is thus recommended to focus on enhancing spatial and temporal resolution of foreground inventory flows. Using several LCIA methods remains a strong recommendation since underlying rationales and assumptions may diverge significantly – and complement each other. By extension, it is also strongly recommended to assess results with all available 'cultural perspectives' (ReCiPe) or 'value choices' (LC-Impact).

2.2. Tier 2 recommendations

We assume that Tier 2 users are more experienced LCA practitioners, with more time available to dig into details. They had enough time and skills to retrieve a full temporal profile of background and foreground GHG emissions, including temporary carbon storage in biomass and soil. Also, they already have followed Tier 1 recommendations and are looking for additional information for decision-making.

Tier 2 users are invited to use additional CFs as proposed by Iordan et al. (2018) and provided as spreadsheets in ALIGNED T1.3 repository (*ALIGNED_Biodiv_CF* excel file). Brightway2 software users may find the procedure to import these CFs in the html file *Biodiv_CF_bw_import*.

Since GHG emissions do not need spatial information, Tier 2 users can reliably apply these CFs on both foreground and background data, with specific emission dates. It is most important to keep consistency between selected SSP scenarios for background data calculated with *premise* (see ALIGNED T1.1 repository files) and RCP scenarios used in Iordan et al. (2018) to compute CFs.

Results obtained with this procedure cannot be added up with operational LCIA methods since they are expressed in different units (cf previous section). However, the modeled additional impacts may prove useful in illustrating the differences between short-term and long-term impacts of climate change on biodiversity.

It is also recommended to run simulation for different SSP-RCP scenarios to secure decision-making.

2.3. Tier 3 recommendations

Tier 3 users are LCA experts and researchers. They already have applied Tiers 1 and 2 recommendations and have found that direct / foreground LULUC impacts are predominant in the product's environmental signature. They also have dedicated additional time to get a high level of spatial resolution in direct / foreground LULUC, using ALIGNED T1.2 repository files.

In addition, Tier 3 users are also familiar with LC-Impact framework and the LULUC impact assessment.

With these conditions, spatially and species explicit CFs from Chaudary & Brooks (2018) can be used on foreground LULUC. Results may be compared with operational methods only for foreground data, since spatial resolution of current background LCI databases remains too coarse (e.g. at national level).

3. Conclusion

Currently, operational LCIA methods propose world-average estimations of damage characterization factors of environmental interventions to ecosystem quality. LCIA method developers strongly insist on the incomprehensiveness of impact pathways covered by their models, as well as the room for improvement in spatial accuracy and time dynamics.

The present guide aims to describe the possibilities for LCA practitioners with different levels of expertise. Operational LCIA methods are briefly described so that least experienced practitioners can easily find the keys for result interpretation. Tier 2 practitioners who already depicted the temporal dynamics of GHG emissions – using recommendations for background and foreground LCI stages – will find complementary damage assessment on ecosystem quality from climate change. Finally, LCA Experts exploring direct impacts from Land Use and Land Use Change are recommended to explore spatially explicit CF dataset as complementary information for decision-making on land management.

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